

INSTRUCTIONAL METHODS FOR LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: This article highlights effective teaching methods which can provide students with opportunities to enhance their English skills (listening, speaking, writing and reading) and develop their learning strategies on my teaching experiences.

Key words: pupils, language skills, reading, writing, speaking, listening, activity, English

Аннотация: В этой статье освещаются эффективные методы обучения, которые могут предоставить учащимся возможность улучшить свои навыки английского языка (аудирование, разговорная речь, письмо и чтение) и разработать свои стратегии обучения на основе моего опыта преподавания.

Ключевые слова: учащиеся, языковые навыки, чтение, письмо, говорение, аудирование, деятельность, английский язык.

Once, Richards (2003) noted that English is the language of globalization. International communication, commerce and trade, media and pop culture, and it affects people's motivation learn. English is no longer a property English speaking but international world Products sometimes called Global English or English As an international language. During the teaching period, I have learned different methods and teaching rules to work with students, because every students have different background English knowledge and different levels. My pupils, all of them similar ages 12 and 13 and all of them have been studying together in a group and all of my students are L2 learners. But their levels are different based on their backgrounds, some of them go to English courses after the lesson to enhance their English skills (listening, speaking, writing and reading). So my students level were beginner, when they started learn English language with me, after 7 months later, I took them test according to ALTE (The Association of Language Testers in Europe) language test. However, after studying effective teaching ways nearly 7 months, their level increased to B1 level. In terms of speaking and listening, they can express their emotions and ideas in limited way, of course, my students have some problems using past tenses to describe past events, when they should describe story or event always my learners use past -ed verbs, not able to use used To Form to express their opinions and they have some problems with fluency during their speech.

Richard (2003) mentioned that "Speaking has always been a major focus of language teaching, however both the nature of speaking skills as well as approaches to teaching them have undergone a major shift in thinking in recent years" (p.2) When it comes to listening skill, my learners struggle with listening comprehension, when they should find right answer from multiple choice questions, they can find hardly only 2 right answers out of 6 multiple questions. Thompson (2004) noted "listening scholars remind us that students spend more time listening as a way to learn than they do using any of the other communication abilities, yet few have opportunities at the undergraduate level to develop listening as a fundamental ability for learning" (p.226).

In terms of reading and writing, they faced to some mistakes to find words which is given reading task gap filling form, my learners struggle to find location which information is given in the reading passage. Another weakness side that they can't link ideas and opinions each

other, they have issue with comprehension. When it comes to writing, their ideas are somehow not linked to each other, they couldn't explain their opinions briefly when they are writing a narrative story.

Reading Activity Outline

Topic	Working with newspaper reading
Objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ To develop reading comprehension ✓ To improve reading details ✓ Students will be able to discuss the news and to understand the meaning of reading passage ✓ Learning and working with grammar and vocabulary by the help of reading task. ✓ To acquire phrase, some idioms and collocations from the activity.
Instructions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Before starting the activity, teacher will divided the class into 3 groups. ● teacher printed reading passage to give students before starting ● Teacher give directions and instructions to read ● One the same reading will be given to each groups. ● There are 2 minutes to fill in specific data from the text. ● 3 minutes will be given to find vocabulary, idioms and collocations. ● Students should make 7 questions based on the reading.(matching, gap filling, multiple choice question and etc.) ● after 5 minutes each group should exchange their questions paper. ● All of the students have to find right answers from each question paper.
Skills:	✍ reading comprehension, good at finding specific data, critical thinking.
Recommendation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✍ Before starting this activity, to do brainstorm and gathering ideas according to the text title ✍ To think background knowledge based on the text.

From this activity, students can take an advantage not only to enhance their reading skills, but also they can also develop their comprehension ability with working group members together. As Richards (2003) noted that "Pair and group activities predominate in the classroom" (p. 17).By the help of the activity, Students will be able to work on the question types, reading and finding answers will give the chance to improve their reading comprehension, when learners read newspaper vocabulary and ideas, they have to think or search the words another meaning which is far from first meaning. The information push the students to think critical or find exact meaning based on the context. From this reading activity, my pupils accommodate their needs' for improving their reading comprehension, because the main issue that they struggle with linking ideas to each other and my pupils have lack of reading comprehension. According to Lee (2013), inference is an essential element in reading comprehension in that such an engagement must be present whenever literal comprehension

takes place” (p.3). It is effective and interesting task for my learners, since they can easily bored to read and only find answers from the reading passage.

Writing task

Topic	Write Invitation Card
Objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Students will be able to use and write adjectives and their own words ● Students will learn grammar tense “Will” form ● Using specific vocabularies ● To enhance creative skill by decorating and writing Initiation card
Instructions:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Teacher explains future tenses clearly ✓ Teacher write 3 sentences according to will form ✓ Teacher write an example invitation card to explain how write it. <p>Teacher write some questions on the blackboard.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. When do you celebrate your party? 2. Who will come your party? 3. what will you do this party and etc.
Skills:	✎ writing skill, comprehensible ability, vocabulary, grammar, creativity ability
Recommendation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Before starting this activity, students should review their previous lessons and grammar structures ✓ To memorize vocabulary based on previous lessons

This writing activity gives students the opportunity to improve their writing skills and creativity. So my pupils can develop their analytical skills while writing and reading initiation cards. To do this writing activity, students need to know what the future tenses are and know important vocabulary from the invitation form. I draw and draw info graphics on the blackboard to make writing easier. As Maamuujav, et. al (2019), stated that “utilizing an info graphic as a communicative and procedural tool allows students to engage in deeper thinking and planning in the early stage of their writing and enables teacher to provide targeted support, feedback, and scaffolding during the initial drafting process” (p. 10).

With the help of this method, my students write anything easily without misunderstanding, also writing invitation card will help them to write their opinions and ideas and they learn link their two ideas to express correctly.

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